

Young Eruptive Stars with the Highest Angular Resolution

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Star formation: From clouds to discs: A Tribute to the Career of Lee Hartmann

Malahide, 2021 October 21

Introduction: why highest resolution?

Rising/fading timescales of eruptive phenomena (~ 1 year) imply physical changes in the inner disk (~ 1 au)

How to explore such an Earth orbit-size world?

- theory: employ Lee Hartmann to construct models and invent ideas
- observations (for us, who are less imaginative): interferometry, time series, spectra

Questions Lee had no time to answer yet...

Structure of the inner disk in young eruptive stars

- typical or aberrant? How similar to normal YSOs?
- what can we learn about the outburst mechanism?

Temporal variability of the system

- response of a perturbed system
- evolution of the outburst: outburst physics?

Impact of the outburst on the terrestrial zone

Feedback to the interstellar medium (outflows, jets)

Infrared: ESO's VLTI Interferometer (VLTI)

MIDI (2003 – 15)

- two telescopes (UTs, ATs)
- spectrally resolved interferometry in the N-band (8 – 13 μm)
- 3 – 4 milli-arcsecond resolution
- interpretation via modeling

MATISSE (2018 –)

- four telescopes
- L (3.5 μm), M (4.8 μm), N (8 – 13 μm)
- image reconstruction

A unique infrared interferometric observatory

Konkoly VLTI Expertise Centre (Budapest, Hungary)

A VLT/MIDI survey of eruptive stars

VLT/MIDI atlas of disks around low- and intermediate-mass young stellar objects:
82 disks, incl. 7 FUors & 4 EXors

Simple 'temperature gradient' model:

- $R_{\text{in}}/R_{\text{sub}}$
- $T \sim r^{-q}$

→ 32/82 disks have $R_{\text{in}}/R_{\text{sub}}$, 1/7 FUor, 2/4 EXor

FUor disks rarely have inner holes.

Radiative transfer models
with/out cavities:
blue - no gap green - gap

A VLT/MIDI survey of eruptive stars

Based on Varga et al. (2018)

Simple temperature gradient model:

$$T(r) = T_{\text{sub}} \left(\frac{r}{R_{\text{sub}}} \right)^{-q}$$

$$\langle q \rangle_{\text{FUor}} = 0.84 \pm 0.31 \quad \text{flat disk?}$$

$$\langle q \rangle_{\text{EXor}} = 0.53 \pm 0.12 \quad \text{flared disk?}$$

FUors may have steeper T-profiles; EXors are typical

The prototype: FU Ori with VLT/MATISSE

MATISSE GTO, 5 epochs (2019/12 – 2021/01), 6 simultaneous baselines.

Inner accretion disk radius
Scale height
Disk mass
Grain size
N-band visibilities

0.2 au
0.17 @100 au
 $2 \times 10^{-2} M_{\text{sun}}$
small + large
0.7-0.9

small
normal
normal/low
atypical
high

RADMC-3D model: inner accretion disk + outer disk (Lykou et al. submitted)
See Poster of Lykou et al.

The MIR emitting region is rather small (imaging project cancelled...)

V900 Mon with VLT/MATISSE

MATISSE OT, 2 epochs
(2019/12 – 2020/01)

Pole-on system

Strong radial spectral
variations

V900 Mon with VLT/MATISSE

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At smaller spatial scales
flux at the 9-11 μm range
is “missing”

Absorbing dust layer above the inner disk?!

Accreting material? Dusty polar outflow? Streamer? Clumps in an envelope?

Azimuthal disk asymmetries?

FU Ori H-band polarization image (Takami et al. 2018)

Closure phases are non-zero. Asymmetry can be caused by inclined disk (modeling).

Results for the pole-on V900 Mon disk are under investigation

No very obvious structures in the inner disk.

Unknown close companions?

Chen et al. in prep.

No unseen companions in the MIDI/MATISSE data of FUors

The fading of V1647 Ori in 2005

2004, Credit: Gemini Observatory

Mosoni et al. (2013)

The fading of V1647 Ori in 2006

Mosoni et al. (2013)

Correlated flux
(inner region):
drop by 2-3x.

Total flux
(whole disk):
drop by <2x.

The relative MIR contributions of compact and extended disk regions changed, opposite to expectations.

Expanding radius of the inner cavity by winds? Time delay due to heat capacity?

V346 Nor: toward quiescence?

Kóspál et al. (2020)

Increased extinction during fading!

Dust condensation?
Rearrangement of the envelope?

Multiepoch accretion disk modeling

The steady optically thick disk

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{M} &= -2\pi R \Sigma v_R \\ T_d^4 &= \frac{3GM\dot{M}}{8\pi R^3\sigma} \left[1 - \left(\frac{R_*}{R} \right)^{1/2} \right] \\ L_\nu &= \int_{R_{in}}^{R_{out}} \pi B_\nu[T_d(R)] 2\pi R dR\end{aligned}$$

Lee Hartmann: Accretion Processes in Star Formation, Sect. 7

Fixed params: R_{in} ($=R_{star}$), R_{out} , distance, inclination

Fitted params: M^*M_{dot} , A_v

Combined with an extinction law, it seems to be a simple but powerful description of FUor SEDs.

Multiepoch accretion disk modeling

Gaia 18dvy (Szegedi-Elek et al. 2020)

Exponential rise for ~ 3 yrs
E-folding time: 145 days

Multiepoch accretion disk modeling

Exponential decay; variable A_V

Radially resolved mineralogy in FUors

- VLTI/MIDI
- Herbig AeBe stars
- Strong radial trend
- Inner part: crystalline silicates
- Outer part: amorphous silicates

- VLTI/MIDI
- FU Orionis
- No radial trend
- Inner part: large particles
- Outer part: large particles

Jets in eruptive stars

Table 1 The FU Ori objects

Object	Outburst	$t(\text{Rise})$	$t(\text{Decay})$	$d(\text{kpc})$	L/L_{\odot}	CO flow	Jet/HH	Ref.
FU Ori	1937	~ 1 yr	~ 100 yr	0.5	500	no	no	a,b,d
V1057 Cyg	1970	~ 1 yr	~ 10 yr	0.6	800–250	yes	no	a,b,d,q
V1515 Cyg	1950s	~ 20 yr	~ 30 yr	1.0	200	no	no	a,b,d
V1735 Cyg	$\sim 1957\text{--}65$	< 8 yr	> 20 yr	0.9	> 75	yes	no	c,d,q
V346 Nor	$\gtrsim 1984$	< 5 yr	> 5 yr	0.7	?	yes	yes	f,k
BBW 76	< 1930	?	~ 40 yr	1.7?	?	?	no	h,i,o
Z CMa	?	?	> 100 yr	1.1	600	yes	yes	d,e,m, n,p
L1551 IRS5	?	?	?	0.15	≥ 20	yes	yes	g,j,l
RNO 1B,C	?	?	?	0.8	?	yes?	no	r,s,t

Jets in high-res spectroscopy

V1057 Cyg

Instruments: Nordic Optical Telescope, Bohyunsan Optical Astronomy Obs.

Strong forbidden emission lines in **V899 Mon**, **V1057 Cyg**; no forbidden lines in **V1515 Cyg**

V899 Mon

Conclusions

There is no inner cavity + the hot disk region is small + T-profile can be steep + analytical model fits the data → standard steady accretion disk is good approximation

There may be matter out of the disk plane, cloudlet encounter theory may work. But there is no sign of non-axisymmetric distribution or close companion

There are measurable temporal changes in the structure of the circumstellar environment during the outburst

Lost crystals have not been found yet

Most FUors may drive jets

My vote: interferometry + time domain + high-res spectroscopy